

Remarketing Features

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ABSTRACT

Remarketing is a term traditionally used to describe further communication with users leaving the site via e-mail. Remarketing help companies to attract customers to their website. Article analysis remarketing definition, remarketing advantages and disadvantages, remarketing strategy and activities.

KEYWORDS: *remarketing, remarketing advantages and disadvantages, remarketing activities*

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I. INTRODUCTION

Remarketing is a remarketing process that allows advertisers to see your customers already familiar to your business. Customers of a product or service usually did not buy it for the first time. A frequent customer wants to learn more before deciding to buy: read reviews, compare prices or consult others. It is common that the first visit does not buy, and then forget the seller's name. Remarketing helps persuade visitors to come back to you and look at products that you have previously been interested in. Purpose of article is to analyze remarketing features, remarketing definition, remarketing advantages and disadvantages, remarketing activities.

II. REMARKETING DEFINITION

Remarketing is a remarketing process that allows you to find past visitors to a website across the Internet and show them ads related to a website. Remarketing helps re-persuade visitors to return to the site and purchase the service they provide. It works through online advertising networks, the largest of which is the Google Display Network, which represents over 1 million popular web portals (these have placed Google AdSense ads on their webpage). The principle of action is based on the display of text, advertising panels and advertising to the target audience. Remarketing is a means to re-attract potential customers who have already visited your website or e-shop, but has not taken any action and left. The purpose of Remarketing is to encourage such visitors to return to your website or e-shop and purchase the goods or services you provide. To achieve this goal, we rely on an effective solution - banner advertising to targeted users on the Google content network. Remarketing is featured on the most popular news

portals and high traffic sites, and on other pages featuring Google standard banners. It's important to understand that the Google system itself determines which pages to display, so the variety of sites is guaranteed!

Remarketing is a way to re-attract potential customers who have already visited your site, but did not take action and left. Remarketing is a way to re-attract potential customers who have already visited your website or e-shop, but did not take action and left. Remarketing is a form of advertising that helps to remind your website visitors about your business by visiting other popular websites with advertising space. Did you know that more than 90% of website visitors leave the site without any action (without signing up for a newsletter without purchasing goods / services without inquiring about the goods / services). The remarketing has been established around 2007 and gained momentum in 2010 when it was officially launched on the Google AdWords platform. Since then, this advertising tool has improved considerably and has a number of forms [6]: .

Site remarketing. This is remarketing in the general sense: showing ads to people who visited the site but not converting. The first ads for retargeting were billboards.

CRM remarketing ads show to people with email You send email addresses to the service provider. The latter has its own database, which allows the submission of e-mails. Email address to identify user online. This is a very effective way to remind yourself not only of website visitors, but also of people who contacted the company in the real world (for example, filled out a questionnaire in a physical store).

Social Remarketing - Ads on social networks for people who visited your site. Retargeting is offered by Facebook, Twitter and YouTube, while LinkedIn does not yet have this capability.

Search Ads Remarketing Lists (RLSA) - Exclusively Google AdWords provides the ability to display text ads in search results for users who have visited your site.

Search remarketing differs from all other forms of remarketing in that they seek to re-reach people who have already been in contact with your business in one way or another. Meanwhile, search remarketing allows you to display advertising banners on other sites for people who

never visited your site but searched for keywords relevant to your business.

Remarketing is process, during which customers are attracted to visit website again , advertising are shown and customers are promoted to buy products. Table 1 show different remarketing definition. Kantola, J. (2014) stated that remarketing can be used target audience, which is interested in product. Arsenault (2012) define that remarketing is marketing tool which attracted customers by cookies. Gürbüz1, A., Kiliç. L., I., Yeğgn, T. (2016) stated that remarketing is internet and traditional marketing strategy. Helft, M., Vega, T. (2010) define remarketing as marketing tool, which show ads timely and timely manner.

Table.1. Remarketing concept

Author	Highlight
Kantola, J. (2014)	Remarketing can be used target customers who have already shown interest in the product and the content of the ads is very high important to them.
Arsenault (2012)	Remarketing is a newer term of online advertising methods when customers are marked with cookies when you visit the site and these cookies are used later redirect the client to online advertising channels.
Gürbüz1, A., Kiliç. L., I., Yeğgn, T. (2016)	Remarketing can be the only one online and traditional marketing advertising strategy. The concept is for customers who already have visited sites and repeatedly showed them.
Helft, M., Vega, T. (2010).	Remarketing, which is personally tailored to the form of marketing, is an invention that tries to show customer ads in a very timely and timely manner..

III. REMARKETING ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

Advantages	Disadvantages
Brand recognition: One of the main and almost definite benefits of reusing is that repetition enhances brand recognition. The more someone sees your brand, the more likely they will recognize it in the future, and the consumers are more likely to buy the product from the brand they know. Enhancement is an essential component of learning, and it is also that reorientation is great. A number of studies have shown that the exposure environment is less important than the exposure itself, and the goals are precisely defined.	Creepy, weird and annoying are three words that are often used to describe retargeting. Too many excitement is the main reason for the complaint - it seems that some retargeters just don't know when to stop.
That somebody visited your site but didn't have anything to buy - it doesn't necessarily mean they decided against it. The Internet is loaded with troubling factors, and Internet users have a very short attention. Maybe someone sent them a funny video, or their phone sounded, or they realized that at the time they just didn't need your product. Without regulation, a potential customer may be lost forever.	This can be ineffective: reusing is particularly annoying for already converted customers - those who have already purchased a purchase or even bought the product they are advertising. Be careful when choosing a retargeter, and choose one that uses segmentation (showing different ads to visitors with different degrees of loyalty, t. Also, make sure the "firing pixel" (a magic line of code that releases a client from targeted ads when they purchase) are included in your Thanksgiving page to save a new customer who is now an unnecessary campaign.
If someone visits your site, there is a good chance that they are at least somewhat interested in what you have to offer. By focusing your advertising efforts on people who have already shown interest in your brand, you just reinforce your existing interest. Unlike other forms of marketing that can offer your message to a wide audience - many of them openly will not listen to your business - retargeting is specifically marketing towards the interested audience. You've reduced the likelihood that your ad will respond.	Some see retargeting as an invasion of privacy - a problem of modern social climate. Repeated application does not collect personally identifiable information, i. Y. Information such as age or gender that can be used to identify a person - many still find it inappropriate. Repeated application is in compliance with laws and regulations, it simply does not feel suitable for some Internet users, and a review of the brand by such means can lead to a negative review of their brand. While many Internet users do not feel that way, some do so, and with reuse, they are inevitably crippled.

IV. REMARKETING STRATEGY

Remarketing process consist three steps[8]:

1. Find out the purpose of return. Remarketing helps only work with visitors who visit your site, so it's important to understand why a visitor has to return to your site a second or more times.
2. Invite to take action. it is important that both the promotional panels you show in remarketing and the site's landing page, which are visited by visitors to this panel, are the elements of the action promotion and their continuity.
3. Returning Information. This step is closely related to the first, but it is worth understanding that if the user returns to the page 3 or more times, the page information itself is familiar to him, so the user is not surprised to see the same content. Information for returning visitors should also vary, depending on what the user has done on the website.

The goal of remarketing strategies and tools is to force consumers to buy goods and services at the lowest possible cost and time. Mass media do not fit this concept. Knowing that repetition users are exposed, but the ad is inappropriate, it is necessary to look for a channel where the repetition of each message is as expedient as possible, both for the user to whom the message is displayed, and where the message is displayed [9].

If you sell products online, refusing a basket will be one of the biggest challenges for your marketing efforts. The good news is that you can use remarketing to drastically reduce your cart refusal rates, and you can use the same method to increase conversions, even if you're not e-mailed. Mail.

Create campaigns for existing customers. It is important to create a good campaign for existing users. You can use e-mail for this purpose. Email marketing, but remarketing reinforces your efforts.

Search advertising remarketing list. You can predict what your buyers are going to look for after they purchase you and direct them to relevant product ads. Get started with email Email registration from remarketing traffic. Promoting website content in social media is the ideal place to start this strategy, even if you can do this with Google ads if you choose the right keywords.

Apply a similar target market. Google and Facebook help reach a new target market. Use dynamic remarketing. Dynamic remarketing makes it easier for users to look at specific products or services on your site.

Major users when shopping. You can monitor user behavior in a variety of ways and target them to different ads, depending on their position in the purchasing process and how their needs change.

Offer more target audiences. Over time, you'll want to try different bidding strategies, but start with many suggestions for high-intelligence audiences Reduced Online Advertising and Cost-per-Action: Relocating ads is a very cost-effective way to reach qualified prospects.

Emarketing benefits not only the entrepreneur but also the browser, whose goal is to quickly find the information he

needs. In order to make remarketing effective, it is important to develop a communication strategy tailored to your specific business. Many entrepreneurs who use the remarketing service mistakenly think that this is just a preparation of the Google Adwords system codes. Believe it is just a technical job that guarantees efficiency. Really not. It is also communication with customers, taking into account their needs.

remarketing Consider what you have to offer to customers to come back to you? What do website visitors turn into buyers? Remarketing effectively contributes to the promotion and reputation of your brand. Continuous "strong support" with customers will encourage them to feel more important.

Search advertising is useful for anyone using Google's search engine:

The remarketing of advertising to the client helps to find the target customers.

The virtual world browser sees the ads that are relevant to it. The advertiser wins because advertising gets attention, and at the same time, potential buyers.

The advertising system earns revenue from every click. It's a service where everyone wins. The most important thing to remember when using remarketing services is to keep in touch with target customers and use visuals that are attractive, relevant, useful.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Remarketing is one of the most targeted and effective forms of advertising on the internet, because advertising is only targeted at people who are involved with this advertising because they are recently interested in the production of a particular company and later browsing the web, seeing it in different places, namely the advertising of this company. If a consumer currently decides which company should buy a service or product, such targeted advertising can encourage the consumer to make a decision. And with a cleverly designed remarketing advertising strategy, repetition of targeted messages to a targeted visitor can increase sales to three or more times [9]. Remarketing is visible only to users who are already interested in your goods or services. Opportunity to publish customized messages and special offers based on visitor's needs, behavior and interests. 90% of lost visitors can be reached and up to 50% returned to the site. Increasing website traffic and sales. Reminds of your services and goods, gives you the opportunity to "convince your visitors by another message", why it's worth your client. Brand awareness and credibility are enhanced. Remarketing directly affects the return on investment of the campaign, no matter what the advertising campaign strategy is: brand-focused, campaign performance, or more. Combining Google Adwords advertising and remarketing campaigns can increase your campaign's conversion rate while increasing your Quality Score, which reduces your campaign costs.

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